

GESIS Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

Survey of academic staff on working conditions, organizational culture and work culture at universities

Questionnaire (English)

*Christine Abraham, Anke Lipinsky, Andrea Löther,
Lara Schmitz*

August 2025

GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

Content

Description	3
Information about the questionnaire.....	3
Welcome Page	4
Module A: Screening & Sociodemographics 1	5
Module B: Organizational Culture, Sense of Belonging, and Thoughts about Leaving Academia	8
Module C: Working Conditions.....	12
Module D: Appointment Negotiations and Assessment of Performance-related Pay for Special Achievements	14
Module E: Work Culture, Support from Supervisor and Colleagues	16
Module F: Involvement in Committees	19
Module G: Sociodemographics 2.....	21
Module H: Experiences with Psychological Violence	23
Module I: Experiences with Sexual Harassment.....	25
Module J: Experiences with Discrimination and Knowledge of Contact Points at University	27
Module K: Work-Life Balance, Psychosocial Well-Being.....	29
Final Page Successful Participation / Screenout	34

Suggested citation:

Christine Abraham, Anke Lipinsky, Andrea Löther, Lara Schmitz (2026). Survey of academic staff on working conditions, organizational culture and work culture at universities. Questionnaire (English). Cologne: GESIS -Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences.

Description

This questionnaire was developed by CEWS – Center for Gender Relations in Academia at GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences for the online survey conducted as part of the study on intersectional gender inequalities in structural and cultural-normative organizational and working conditions at universities (SIGIS). Academic staff at eight German universities were surveyed.

The questions were developed based on questions and items from existing surveys on the working and organizational climate and gender relations in academia. The questionnaire was created in consultation with the participating universities and reviewed by the data protection officers of the universities and GESIS. The GESIS Ethics Committee reviewed and approved the questionnaire. CEWS conducted cognitive and quantitative pre-tests. Programming and testing were carried out by CEWS using the Unipark survey software.

Further publications within the framework of the SIGIS project:

- Method Report of the online survey (after project completion in June 2026): [GESIS Papers](#)
- Handout on prevention and dealing with attacks in the context of online surveys: [GESIS Papers](#)
- Overall report of the SIGIS study (after the end of the project in June 2026): [CEWS/publik – Reports on gender equality in science](#)
- Survey data set (after the end of the project in June 2026): <https://www.gesis.org/en/landingpage/data-tesis>
- Questionnaire in German:
Abraham, C., Lipinsky, A., Löther, A., & Schmitz, L. (2026). *Online-Befragung des wissenschaftlichen Personals an Hochschulen zu Arbeitsbedingungen, Organisations- und Arbeitskultur. Fragebogen (deutsch)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18754967>

Information about the Questionnaire

[Purple: Filter guide Screenout and input filter (== means equal; != means not equal; > means greater than; < means less than). These are not visible in the questionnaire.]

[Grey: Placeholder for university-specific adjustments, e.g., names of universities, link lists to help services for psychological violence and sexual harassment]

- Radio button (only one answer option can be selected)
- Checkbox (multiple answers possible)

Welcome Page

Welcome to the survey of academic staff at [Name of university]!

The survey is being conducted by GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences on behalf of [Name of university].

The survey focuses on how working conditions and work and organizational culture are perceived by the academic staff at your university.

Your participation in the online survey is **anonymous** and **voluntary**. None of the answers you provide in this survey can be traced back to you personally. No data that could be used to identify you is collected.

The survey will take about **15 minutes** to complete. You can stop the survey at any time.

The survey contains questions of a sensitive nature on psychosocial well-being and experiences of psychological abuse, sexual harassment, and discrimination in the university context. Information about support services can be found at the appropriate point in the questionnaire. The research team attaches great importance to compliance with ethical and data protection standards in the survey. The questionnaire has been approved by the GESIS Ethics Committee.

After the study has been completed, GESIS will transfer the anonymous and curated survey data to [Name of university]. In addition, a data set from all universities involved in the study will be used for academic publications and made available for subsequent use in teaching and research.

If you have any questions, please contact the GESIS research team: befragung-sigis@gesis.org

- I would like to participate in the survey and agree to the processing, storage, and use of my data.

Button “continue”

Module A: Screening & Sociodemographics 1

v1: Do you currently have an employment contract with [Name of university]?

[Employment contracts with the teaching hospital,] service contracts (Werkvertrag), fee agreements, remunerated teaching assignments, and scholarships are not included here.

If you are a tenured professor at [Name of university], please select 'yes'.

- (1) yes
- (2) no (**Screenout 1**)

v2: Which of the following employee groups at [Name of university] would describe you?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) Science staff (includes: doctoral/habilitation candidates, postdoctoral researchers, academic assistants, academic (senior) advisors, senior engineers, science staff in medicine)
- (2) W1 professors
- (3) W2-W3 and C2-C4 professors (includes: substitute professors, assistant professors, and full-time visiting professors)
- (4) Teachers with special responsibilities (includes: (senior) teachers in higher education, subject teachers)
- (5) Graduate assistants (wissenschaftliche Hilfskräfte) (**Screenout 2**)
- (6) Student assistants (studentische Hilfskräfte) (**Screenout 2**)
- (7) Technical and administrative staff (**Screenout 2**)

- (8) None of the above (**Screenout 2**)

v3: What is your highest academic qualification?

- (1) I do not have a degree.
- (2) Degree (BA, MA, diploma, state examination, or similar)
- (3) Doctorate or PhD
- (4) Habilitation or equivalent qualification

v4: Where are you employed at your university?

- (1) in a faculty/department, chair or institute
- (2) in a central service unit (e.g., research center, center for professional development, computer center, library)
- (3) in central administration

v5: Does your work involve research activities?

By research, we mean: creative, experimental, and systematic work carried out to expand a body of knowledge and develop new applications of existing knowledge.

- (1) yes
- (2) no

v6: Broadly speaking, which academic field does your work at [Name of university] fall under?

- (1) Mathematics and natural sciences (including biotechnology, geography, environmental sciences, etc.)
- (2) Engineering (including computer science, technology, civil engineering, industrial engineering, etc.)
- (3) Human medicine and health sciences (including clinical medicine, dentistry, etc.)
- (4) Agricultural, forestry, and food sciences (including veterinary medicine, etc.)
- (5) Law, economics, and social sciences (including education, psychology, etc.)
- (6) Humanities (including history, languages, sport, art, etc.)
- (7) **Filter: v 4!=1 OR v5!=1 Not applicable.**

We would now like to ask you a few questions about yourself.

v7: What year were you born in? Please select your year of birth...

- Year of birth (Range: 1935;2006)

v8: Which gender do you identify as?

- (1) woman
- (2) man
- (3) non-binary
- (4) agender
- (5) a further gender not listed here
- (6) *I prefer not to say.*

v9: What is your legally registered gender?

- (1) male
- (2) female
- (3) diverse or a further gender not listed here
- (4) no gender entry

Module B: Organizational Culture, Sense of Belonging, and Thoughts about Leaving Academia

The following questions are about how you feel at your university.

v10: How connected do you feel with [Name of university] and with academia in general?

with my immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.)

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

Filter: v4==1 with my department/faculty

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

Filter: v4==2 with the central service unit

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

Filter: v4==3 with the central administration

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

with my university

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

with the academic community of my discipline(s)

- (1) not at all connected
- (2) not very connected
- (3) somewhat connected
- (4) very connected
- (5) *Not applicable*

v11: We would now like to ask you about your thoughts on staying at your university and academia in general. In the last 12 months, how often have you thought about each of the following?

changing your immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.)?

- (1) never
- (2) a few times a year
- (3) a few times a month
- (4) a few times a week
- (5) every day

changing universities?

- (1) never
- (2) a few times a year
- (3) a few times a month
- (4) a few times a week
- (5) every day

leaving academia?

- (1) never
- (2) a few times a year
- (3) a few times a month
- (4) a few times a week
- (5) every day

v12: To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the work atmosphere at [Name of university]?

The work atmosphere in my immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.) is competitive.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree

The work atmosphere at my university is competitive.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree

v13: And what about the following statements regarding the work atmosphere at [Name of university]? Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the statements.

The work atmosphere in my immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.) is cooperative.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree

The work atmosphere at my university is cooperative.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree

v14: To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding recognition, support, and employee voice at [Name of university]?

I have to invest more time and effort than some of my colleagues at [Name of university] in order to receive the same recognition.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

At [Name of university], I generally receive support from faculty leaders when I ask for it.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

I feel that I can help shape important strategic aspects within [Name of university].

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

Module C: Working Conditions

Now we will ask you a few questions about your contractual working conditions at [Name of university].

v15: When did you start working at [Name of university]? Please select...

- Year (Range: 1960;2025)

v16: Is your current employment contract a fixed-term contract or a permanent contract?

If you have more than one employment contract with your university, please refer to the contract with the greatest number of hours.

- (1) fixed-term, temporary or contractual
- (2) permanent, tenured or open-ended

v17: *Filter: v16==1* Please enter the total length of your current fixed-term contract in months.

Please select the total length of the contract, not how much of the contract period still remains.

- Total length of current contract (in months): (Range: 1; more than 72)

v18: What is the current volume of your employment?

If you have more than one employment contract with your university, please add up the total working hours from all your employment contracts.

- (1) Full-time (100%)
- (2) Part-time (more than 75%)
- (3) Part-time (more than 50% up to 75%)
- (4) Part-time (more than 25% up to 50%)
- (5) Part-time (25% or less)

v19: Filter: v18>1 Why are you working part-time?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) The position was advertised as such or was offered to me as such.
- (2) So that I have more time for family responsibilities/caregiving (looking after children or persons in need of care).
- (3) So that I have more time for my studies (doctorate, habilitation, professional development).
- (4) I couldn't find a full-time position.
- (5) So that I have more time for professional activities outside the university.
- (6) So that I have more time for my private life.
- (7) For health reasons.
- (8) Other.

v20: Working at a university can involve a variety of tasks, from research and student supervision to organizational duties. In this question, we would like to find out what your work at the university entails.

How were your activities allocated to the following tasks in the last 6 months?

Please allocate your activities to the following tasks as a percentage. The total should add up to 100 percent.

- (1) Research (including publications, lectures, acquisition of external funding, science communication, innovation, and transfer) ____ (%)
- (2) Teaching and examination duties (including preparation and follow-up of courses) ____ (%)
- (3) Supervision of students and doctoral candidates (e.g., bachelor or master theses, dissertations) ____ (%)
- (4) Providing expert opinion and peer reviews (manuscripts, grant applications, evaluations) ____ (%)
- (5) Academic self-administration (e.g., committee work) ____ (%)
- (6) Management and organizational tasks (including personnel management) ____ (%)
- (7) Service and infrastructure tasks for the university (e.g., maintenance work, library, IT) ____ (%)
- (8) Other ____ (%)

v21: Do you do any paid work in addition to your employment at this university?

This includes, for example, employment with social security contributions, marginal employment (minijob), or self-employment/freelance work.

- (1) yes
- (2) no

Module D: Appointment Negotiations and Assessment of Performance-related Pay for Special Achievements

The following questions concern your experiences in your own appointment negotiations at [Name of university] and your assessment of performance-related pay for special achievements.

v22: *Filter: v2==2 OR v2==3* To what extent do the following statements apply to your own appointment negotiations at [Name of university]?

When preparing for my appointment negotiations, I informally sought information from people I knew personally.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I prepared for my appointment negotiations using professional services (e.g., from the German Association of University Professors and Lecturers).

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I found the atmosphere during my appointment negotiations to be respectful.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

During my appointment negotiations at [Name of university], it was important to me that my professorship was well-resourced (in terms of personnel, material resources, and space).

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

During my appointment negotiations at [Name of university], it was important to me that the remuneration was high.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I am satisfied with the outcome of my appointment negotiations.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

v23: Filter: v2==2 OR v2==3 To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding the performance-related pay for special achievements at [Name of university]?

The procedures for awarding performance-related pay for special achievements at [Name of university] are transparent.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

The procedures for awarding performance-related pay for special achievements at [Name of university] are fair.

- ((1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

The criteria for awarding performance-related pay for special achievements seem reasonable to me.

- (1) disagree
- (2) somewhat disagree
- (3) somewhat agree
- (4) agree
- (5) *Not applicable*

Module E: Work Culture, Support from Supervisor and Colleagues

The next few questions relate to your immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.) at the university.

v24: Filter: v2==1 OR v2==2 OR v2==4 To what extent do the following statements apply to your supervisor?

My supervisor is there for me when I need support.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) *I do not have a supervisor.*

I feel that my supervisor criticizes me unfairly, bullies me, or embarrasses me in front of others.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) *I do not have a supervisor.*

My supervisor supports me in my professional development.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) *I do not have a supervisor.*

My supervisor provides me with contacts to people and institutions that facilitate my professional development.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) *I do not have a supervisor.*

Filter: v5==1 My supervisor makes it possible for me to participate in important conferences in my field.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) *I do not have a supervisor.*

Filter: v5==1 My supervisor supports me in my work on academic publications.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies
- (5) I do not have a supervisor.

v25: Are you responsible for other employees as a supervisor?

By supervisor, we mean persons who have a managerial responsibility for other employees and are authorized to issue instructions to these persons.

If you supervise only student assistants, research assistants, and/or interns, please select "no".

- (1) yes
- (2) no

v26: Filter: v25==1 What values and principles are important to you in your leadership role? Please select the most important aspect.

- (1) Promoting diversity and equal opportunities.
- (2) Providing a family-friendly workplace environment.
- (3) Creating an environment in which everyone feels appreciated.
- (4) Promoting excellent results and performance from my staff.

v27: The following questions are about cooperation with colleagues in your immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, institute, etc.).

How often do you receive help and support from your colleagues when needed?

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

How often are your colleagues willing to listen to your work problems when needed?

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

How often do you ask colleagues for feedback on academic papers and presentations?

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always
- (6) *Not applicable*

Module F: Involvement in Committees

Now we are going to look at your involvement in committees at your university.

v28: In the last 24 months, which committees have you been a member of?

Please select each committee at your university which you are currently a member of or in which you hold a leadership position.

- (1) Senate
- (2) University council (Hochschulrat/Universitätsrat)/foundation board (Stiftungsrat)/board of trustees (Kuratorium)
- (3) Commission/committee at university level (e.g., for budget, course quality, ethics, research, or equality)
- (4) Formal working group set up by university management
- (5) Faculty council /faculty board (Fakultätsrat/Fachbereichsrat)
- (6) Commission/committee at faculty or institute level (e.g., for courses and teaching, research, doctorates and habilitation, or equality)
- (7) Appointments committee (Berufungskommission)
- (8) Formal working group set up by the Dean's office/faculty council
- (9) Other

- (10) *I have not been a member of any committee at my university in the last 24 months.*

v29: Filter: v28<10 To what extent do the following statements apply to your committee work at [Name of university]?

If you are involved in several committees, please consider the committee that you personally consider to be the most important.

The time commitment is manageable.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I can help shape issues.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I can influence decisions.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

The work is well structured and effective.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

The decisions made have no consequences, or they are overturned by higher authorities.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

My work for the committee is appreciated by colleagues in my immediate team.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

Module G: Sociodemographics 2

Now we would like to ask you a few more questions about yourself.

v30: How many of your parents or people responsible for your upbringing have a university degree?

- (1) neither person
- (2) one person
- (3) both persons
- (4) more than two persons (for blended families or similar)

- (5) *Not applicable*

v31: How would you rate your own financial situation in the current phase of your life?

- 1 - very poor
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 - very good

v32: Do you have a disability or chronic illness?

- (1) yes
- (2) no

- (3) *I prefer not to say.*

v33: *Filter: v32==1* Is it apparent to others that you have a disability or chronic illness?

- (1) Yes, others can tell that I have a disability or chronic illness when they first meet me.
- (2) Yes, others probably realize after some time that I have a disability or chronic illness.
- (3) No, my disability or chronic illness is not easily apparent to others.

- (4) *I don't know.*

v34: Which of the following terms best describe your sexual orientation?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) asexual
- (2) bisexual
- (3) heterosexual
- (4) homosexual
- (5) pansexual
- (6) a sexual orientation not listed here

- (7) *I prefer not to say.*

v35: Racial discrimination is experienced primarily by people who are perceived as “foreign” or “non-white.” How often are you perceived as “foreign” or “non-white” at your university?

- (1) never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

- (6) *I don't know.*
- (7) *I prefer not to say.*

Module H: Experiences with Psychological Violence

We would now like to ask you some questions about your personal experiences of psychological violence and harassment by people at your university. Psychological violence is any act that causes psychological and/or emotional harm to a person.

If you need help or support, you can find information at the end of this survey or by clicking here.

[LINK contact list: Helpline and services offered by universities]

v36: Have you experienced any of the following at your university in the last 12 months?

- (1) Abusive comments have been made to you (e.g., demeaning, humiliating, offensive or ridiculing comments).
- (2) Threatening comments have been made to you.
- (3) You have been looked at in a hostile manner, stared at, or sneered at.
- (4) You have been interrupted, had someone speak over you, or have been addressed in disrespectful terms in the presence of others.
- (5) You were unfairly given a lower rating than you deserved in an assessment or evaluation.
- (6) You were ignored or not spoken to.
- (7) You were subjected to an outburst of anger.

- (8) *No, none of these things have happened to me.*
- (9) *I prefer not to say.*

v37: Filter: v36 <8 In the previous question, you indicated that you have been subjected to at least one of the situations described. We would be grateful if you could answer three follow-up questions on the subject. You can skip questions if you feel uncomfortable answering them.

You said that in the last 12 months someone [Item text Question v36]. How often did this happen in the last 12 months?

- (1) once
- (2) two to five times
- (3) six times or more

- (4) *I prefer not to say.*

v38: Filter: v36 <8 Who in your university did this to you?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) a superior or supervisor
- (2) a colleague
- (3) someone in a lower position than you, e.g., a member of your team or an assistant
- (4) a student

- (5) *I prefer not to say.*

v39: Filter: v36 <8 Who specifically was it?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) one or more women
- (2) one or more men
- (3) a group of women and men
- (4) other person(s) whose gender was not clearly identifiable

- (5) *I prefer not to say.*

Module I: Experiences with Sexual Harassment

We would now like to ask you some questions about your personal experiences with sexual harassment by people at your university. This includes unwanted verbal, nonverbal, or physical behavior of a sexual nature, such as comments about your appearance or body, receiving pictures with sexual content, sexist jokes, or touching. You can skip questions if you feel uncomfortable answering them.

If you need help or support, you can find information at the end of this survey or by clicking [here](#).

[LINK contact list: Helpline and services offered by universities]

v40: Have you experienced any of the following at your university in the last 12 months?

- (1) You were asked intrusive questions about your private life.
- (2) You were stared at or leered at in an inappropriate manner.
- (3) You were subjected to sexually suggestive comments or jokes.
- (4) Intrusive comments were made about your appearance.
- (5) You received inappropriate invitations to go out.
- (6) Someone exposed themselves to you.
- (7) You were made watch or look at pornographic material against your wishes.
- (8) You were touched, hugged, or kissed in an unwanted manner.

- (9) *No, none of these things have happened to me.*
- (10) *I prefer not to say.*

v41: Filter: v40<9 In the previous question, you indicated that someone has subjected you to at least one of the things described. We would be grateful if you could answer three follow-up questions on the subject. You can skip questions if you feel uncomfortable answering them.

You said that in the last 12 months someone [Item text Question v40]. How often did this happen in the last 12 months?

- (1) once
- (2) two to five times
- (3) six times or more

- (4) *I prefer not to say.*

v42: Filter: v40<9 Who in your university did this to you?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) a superior or supervisor
- (2) a colleague
- (3) someone in a lower position than you, e.g., a member of your team or an assistant
- (4) a student

- (5) *I prefer not to say.*

v43: Filter: v40<9 Who specifically was it?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) one or more women
- (2) one or more men
- (3) a group of women and men
- (4) other person(s) whose gender was not clearly identifiable

- (5) *I prefer not to say.*

Module J: Experiences with Discrimination and Knowledge of Contact Points at University

v44: Have you felt disadvantaged against or unfairly treated at your university in the last 12 months for any of the following reasons?

Please select all that apply.

- (1) because others do not perceive me as German
- (2) because of my German language skills
- (3) because of my skin color
- (4) because of my sexual orientation
- (5) because of my gender
- (6) because of my religion
- (7) because of a disability or chronic illness
- (8) because of my weight
- (9) because of my age
- (10) because of my financial situation
- (11) because I come from a non-academic household
- (12) because of my family responsibilities toward children or relatives
- (13) because of my name
- (14) for other reasons

- (15) *No, I have not experienced any discrimination or unfair treatment in the last 12 months.*

v45: Are you aware of the contact points at your university for the following areas?

Please select all areas for which you know of a contact point at your university. If a contact point covers several areas, please select all the relevant areas.

- (1) Racism
- (2) Anti-discrimination
- (3) Sexual harassment and violence
- (4) Gender Equality
- (5) Family
- (6) Gender diversity and sexual orientation
- (7) Digital abuse
- (8) Psychosocial and mental health
- (9) Disability and chronic illness
- (10) Antisemitism
- (11) Other contact points

- (12) *I am not aware of any contact points.*

v46: How confident are you that your university will support you in the event of discrimination?

- (1) not at all confident
- (2) not really confident
- (3) neutral
- (4) somewhat confident
- (5) completely confident

v47: Now we would like to ask you about your opinion on gender equality policy in general.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about legal regulations?

Legal regulations in the German General Equal Treatment Act (AGG), which are intended to protect certain groups of people from discrimination and promote them in particular, contradict the meritocratic principle in science and academia.

- (1) I disagree completely.
- (2) I disagree somewhat.
- (3) I neither agree nor disagree.
- (4) I agree somewhat.
- (5) I agree completely.

It is necessary to have a legal requirement that women be given preference in areas where they are underrepresented, provided they have the same qualifications and subject matter expertise (e. g. in hiring for jobs).

- (1) I disagree completely.
- (2) I disagree somewhat.
- (3) I neither agree nor disagree.
- (4) I agree somewhat.
- (5) I agree completely.

Module K: Work-Life Balance, Psychosocial Well-Being

Now we would like to ask about the balance between your professional and private life and your well-being.

v48: How many hours do you currently spend on average per day during the week (Mon-Fri) on the following activities?

Please indicate the time spent on each activity in full hours. The total should add up to 24 hours. Small deviations due to rounding to full hours are acceptable.

- (1) sleep: ___ hours
- (2) work for my university (on site or working from home, including breaks): ___ hours
- (3) commuting: ___ hours
- (4) household tasks (including shopping, cooking): ___ hours
- (5) caregiving responsibilities (e.g., raising children, caring for relatives): ___ hours
- (6) leisure activities: ___ hours
- (7) other: ___ hours

v49: To what extent do the following statements about the balance between work and private life apply to you?

The demands of my work interfere with my private life.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I have to change my plans for private or family activities because of work commitments.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

My work drains so much of my energy that it has a negative effect on my private life.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

My work takes up so much time that it has a negative impact on my private life.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

I also do work-related tasks outside of my working hours.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

In my free time, I am available to people I work with.

- (1) does not apply
- (2) does not really apply
- (3) somewhat applies
- (4) applies

v50: These questions are about how you have been in the past three months.

How often have you had stomach ache, headache or tension in various muscles?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you been physically exhausted?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you slept badly or restlessly or found it hard to go to sleep?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you been emotionally exhausted or felt worn out?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you been irritable or tense?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you had problems to concentrate?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

How often have you felt sad or guilty?

- (1) never
- (2) once
- (3) two to five times
- (4) six times or more

v51: How often do the following statements apply to you?

I am full of energy at work.

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

I am enthusiastic about my work.

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

I am completely absorbed in my work.

- (1) never/almost never
- (2) rarely
- (3) sometimes
- (4) often
- (5) always

v52: Finally, we would like to ask you about your overall job satisfaction. How would you rate the following aspects of your current work?

Relationship with students

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Cooperation with colleagues

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Recognition by colleagues at your university for your professional achievements

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Type of conflict resolution in your immediate workplace environment (team, working group, chair, etc.)

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Time for research

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Autonomy in your work

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Work atmosphere

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Career prospects

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Professional position achieved

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Level of salary or remuneration

- (1) very poor
- (2) somewhat poor
- (3) so-so
- (4) somewhat good
- (5) very good
- (6) *Not applicable*

Final Page Successful Participation / Screenout

End survey

You have now reached the end of the survey. If you would like to complete the survey, please click on "Continue."

End page

You have now reached the end of the survey. Thank you very much for your participation. Please close the browser window to exit the survey.

In this survey, you were asked about your personal experiences with psychological violence, sexual harassment, and discrimination in a university context. If you have experienced or observed any of these issues and/or would like to talk to someone about them, please click here. There you will find support services.

Screenout 1

Unfortunately, you are not part of our target group. Only people who have an employment contract with [Name of university] can participate in the survey. We would nevertheless like to thank you very much for your interest.

Screenout 2

Unfortunately, you are not part of our target group. Only people who work as research assistants, professors, and teachers with special responsibilities or lecturers can participate in the survey. We would nevertheless like to thank you very much for your interest.